

Microbial load estimation of selected hotels' swimming pool water in Awka, the Capital City of Anambra State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: A swimming pool holds water to enable swimming and other leisure activities. They can be built underground or above ground. They occur in ocean liners and cruise ships. Underground pools are constructed from concrete, stone, metal, plastic, or fiberglass. Their sizes and shapes can vary. Swimming pools are used for activities such as bathing, wading, exercising, or cooling off on hot days. The quality of swimming pool water must be good. This is due to the

risk of exposure to the body's orifices during swimming. Disinfection of swimming pools is necessary to prevent outbreaks of infectious illnesses **Aim:** This study aimed to estimate the microbial load of selected hotels' swimming pool water in Awka, Anambra State, in Nigeria. **Methods:** A total of 40 water samples were collected from ten swimming pools (A-J) located within popular hotels and suites in Awka, Capital territory. The samplings were made during the weekend when the pools were usually busy. *In situ* measurements were carried out for pH and temperature. The microbial load was evaluated using standard laboratory swimming pool methods. **Results:** On average, considering dry and rainy seasons, 50% of the hotels' swimming pools complied with World Health Organization and United States Environmental Protection Agency acceptable limits for *Escherichia coli*; 100% complied with Coliforms; and 65% complied with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. **Conclusion:** These swimming pools selected in Awka, Anambra State capital, were relatively safe for recreational activities, though there were rooms for improvement.

Key words: Hotels, microbial load, pool operators, suites.

Introduction

A swimming pool holds water to enable swimming and other leisure activities. They can be built underground or above ground. They occur in ocean liners and cruise ships. (WHO, 2011). Underground pools are constructed from concrete, stone, metal, plastic, or fiberglass. Their sizes and shapes can vary. Swimming pools are used for activities such as bathing, wading, exercising, or cooling off on hot days. The quality of swimming pool water must be good. This is due to the risk of exposure to the body's orifices during swimming. Disinfection of swimming pools is necessary to prevent outbreaks of infectious illnesses (Olayemi *et al.*, 2020).

In Awka metropolis, the swimming pool is one of the recreational facilities patronized by different classes of people for leisure or pleasure in most of the hotels or guest houses. However, the swimming pools may harbor different pathogenic microorganisms from infected swimmers or from contaminated water sources or from airborne contamination, or from an ineffective treatment of the swimming pools (Verla *et al.*, 2021). Swimming pools can expose swimmers to physicochemical and microbiological risks. (Hassanein *et al.*, 2023). The number of swimming pools is on the increase, and information about their sanitary condition is scanty; water quality monitoring units are lacking in most of these pools. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), National legislation may include different sets of regulations that will apply to swimming pools and similar recreational environments. Regulation may control, for example, the design and construction of pools, their operation, and management (WHO, 2006). Some swimming pools can actually have high bacterial load, which demonstrates the need for pool health authorities to improve surveillance, improve pool decontamination standards, and educate swimmers on hygiene before entering pools (Okoruwa *et al.*, 2023).

There is currently little or no data about infectious outbreaks of diseases in swimming pools in Awka, despite the fact that there is a high risk of infection due to non-compliance and non-enforcement of regulations regarding the establishment and maintenance of the pools to meet microbiological standards. It is of utmost importance to investigate the health and hygiene of swimming pools for microbial load in Awka metropolis and Nigeria at large to ascertain the extent of the contamination levels in swimming pools, as well as compliance of swimming pools with international standards. There are five bacteriological standards that public pools must meet. They are as follows:

Table 1: Bacteriological water quality requirement for swimming pool.

Test	Standard	Comment
E. coli	0 per 100 ml sample Note: repeat sample must be taken to confirm presence of E. coli	Indicator of the effectiveness of disinfection and recent fecal contamination
Staphylococcus aureus	50 or less per 100 ml sample	Indicator of water contamination
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	10 or fewer per 100 ml of sample	This organism is a pathogen in pools, Spas and whirlpools.
Standard Plate Count	250 or fewer per 1 ml of sample	Indicator of a deficiency in the treatment process

Sources: Department of Health and Community Services Public Health Division, 2019.

Swimming pool water is often heated, and this means it is just the right temperature to provide certain bacteria with the perfect habitat. Viruses and other pathogens can also be present. The symptoms caused by the various microorganisms are similar to one another and are therefore referred to in general terms as ‘recreational waterborne illnesses’ or RWIs. RWIs can be spread by swallowing, breathing, or having contact with germs in the water (US CDC, 2025). Even if a pool looks clean, if it is not properly managed, it can provide harmful bacteria with an ideal environment in which to flourish. This study aimed to estimate the microbial load of selected hotels' swimming pool water in Awka, Anambra State, in Nigeria.

Literature review

Swimming pools are facilities found in recreational places such as hotels, guest houses, and parks. They are for public use. Consequently, they are prone to contamination with microorganisms. Most of these organisms are dangerous to health. Some of the microorganisms commonly found in swimming pools are intestinal coccidia, *Giardia lamblia*, *Microsporidia* spp., *Blastocystis* spp., and *Acanthameba* spp. (Hassanein *et al.*, 2023). Other bacteria that have been found in swimming pools belong to *Pseudomonas*, *Klebsiella*, *Aeromonas*, *Shigella*, *Proteus*, and *Staphylococcus* species. Fungi are not left out in swimming pools. Some notable ones are *Absidia cylindrospora*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus repens*, *Cephalosporium corda*, *Cladosporium*, *Fusarium* sp, *Monotospora altissima*, *Penicillium citrinum*, *Schizophyta minuta*, and *Trichophyton* sp. The coliforms isolated were *Shigella dysenteriae*, *Shigella paradysenteriae*, *Shigella sonnei*, and *Citrobacter freundii*. (Ajadi and Thonda, 2017). However, some swimming pools complied with World Health Organization (WHO) acceptable limits. Those pools that do not comply should be subjected to intense treatment, taking into cognizance the health implications they pose to the public. (Yedeme *et al.*, 2017). Apart from the use of swimming pools for recreational activities, they are also used for sports. Therefore, if they are poorly managed, athletes will be exposed to one illness or the other. These illnesses can be transmitted through swallowing, inhalation, or contact with contaminated water and surfaces. (Tarikuwa *et al.*, 2024). Even though numerous studies have been done to assess the microbial quality of swimming pools, there has not been any such research reported in Awka, the State Capital of Anambra State, in Nigeria. This current study, therefore, filled this knowledge gap while providing an insight into the safety of the swimming pools in this part of the country, Nigeria.

Materials and methods

Materials/Reagents

Desiccators, Methyl Orange, Phenolphthalein, Eriochrome Black T, Erlenmeyer Reflux Flask, Condenser, Hot Plate, Petri dishes, Cover glasses, Potassium Chromate Indicator, Eosin Methylene Blue, 0.1 M Tetraoxosulphate (VI) acid, Silver trioxonitrate (V) solution, Total Hardness Buffer Sol (pH10), Di-Sodium EDTA Solution (1), Murexide/NaCl indicator, Ammonium Chloride, Conc. Tetraoxosulphate (VI) acid Analer grade, Ammonium Molybdate, Ammonium Vanadate, Trioxonitrate (V) acid, Analer grade, Anhydrous Sodium Sulphate, Barium Chloride, Potassium Nitrate, KNO₃, Chloroform (ACS grade), Brucine, Magnesium Sulphate, Alkali-iodide-azide solution, Phosphate buffer, Calcium chloride, Iron (III) Chloride, Glucose azide broth, CdSO₄·8H₂O, K₂Cr₂O₇, CuSO₄·5H₂O, Ferrous Ammonium Sulphate, KMnO₄, Zinc Pellets, Ni (NH₄)₂ (SO₄)₆·H₂O, (CH₃COO)₂Pb or Pb(NO₃)₂, Distilled water, Potassium Chloride (KCl), Borax (Na₂B₄O₇·10H₂O), Sodium sulphide, Glacial acetic acid, BOD Bottles

Equipment

Model Buck Scientific VGP 210 Spectrophotometer (AAS), Model 3305 Jenway pH meter, Model 470 Electroconductivity Meter, Model Spectronic 21D Milton Roy Turbidimeter, Model AE 2005 Mettler Analytical balance, Gallen Kamp Incubator, Model E240 Tamsun Oven, Thermometer, Mercury-in-Glass 10 – 110 °C.

Sample Collection

Water samples were collected from ten different swimming pools in popular hotels in Awka metropolis. Samples were collected directly into clean and air-dried plastic containers that had not been used at three different points and mixed. Samples were collected during the day when pools were in use. On-site, sterile glass reagent bottles were used for the collection of water samples for microbiological analysis and biological oxygen demand. All samples were labeled and stored carefully. Samples preservation was done according to prescribed procedures (Arnold

et al., 2018). Samples were kept in a cooler at about 4 °C prior to transportation to the laboratory, where they were further preserved before analysis within 24 hours of sampling.

Determination of Microbiological Organisms

Determination of Total Coliform as an Indicator Organism

The method used for the extraction of the coliform load was the multiple tube fermentation technique, also referred to as the most probable number (MPN), and the test is of threefold or phases: the presumptive, confirmed, and complete test.

Presumptive Test

A series of serial dilutions of each water sample was made: 1ml from each of the serial dilutions was transferred to each of five fermentation tubes containing suitable lactose culture medium in an inverted gas collection tube: the inoculated tubes were incubated in a water bath at 35.1 0.5 °C for 24 + 2 hours. The accumulation of gas in the inverted gas collection tubes after 24 hours is considered to be a positive reaction. The number of positive tubes was recorded, and the most probable number (MPN) of coliforms was determined per 100 ml of water sample with reference to the MPN index table.

Confirmatory Test

All the presumptive positive tubes were subjected to this second test with Eosin methylene blue. The plates were streaked in such a way as to produce good isolation of colonies. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours to detect the presence of coliforms. Typical colonies, which were nucleated with a greenish metallic sheen, were considered a positive test, while nucleated pinkish colonies yielded a negative test.

Complied Test

Colonies from the confirmed test were used to inoculate a nutrient agar plate, and MacConkey broth was incubated at 37 °C for hours. After incubation, the MacConkey broth was examined

for acid and gas production, and then Gram-stained and examined for the presence of gram-negative bacteria (reddish pink in color). The demonstration of the organism to be gram-negative, as non-spore-forming rods in shape, was considered a satisfactory test that was completed (Mahmoud *et al.*, 2017).

Determination of *E. coli* as an Indicator Organism

Five fresh tubes containing double-strength and two times single-strength MacConkey broth each were inoculated with presumptive positive tubes of 1.0 ml and 0.1 ml for 24.48 hours for *E. coli* counts. Formation of acid and gas within the incubation period in the Durham tubes proved the presence of *E. coli*; the most probable number (MPN) of *E. coli* was determined per 100 ml of water sample with reference to the MPN index table. The presence of a metallic sheen on an eosin methylene blue agar plate was considered a satisfactory test for *E. coli* (Mahmoud *et al.*, 2017).

Determination of Aerobic Mesophilic Count

Serial dilutions of the water samples and the Helbert counting chamber were prepared. A few drops of methylene blue solution were then added to the water sample dilutions. A loop full of water sample (including the various dilutions) was placed on the ruled area of the counting chamber. The chamber was allowed to rest on the bench for 5 minutes for even distribution and settlement of bacteria present in the aliquot of the water sample. The chamber was then examined under a microscope, using a 4 mm x 16 objective lens. To count the bacteria, 50 – 100 squares were selected at random, so that the total number of bacteria was about 500 for each sample. A triplicate count was divided by the number of squares, and the result was multiplied by the dilution factor and a constant K (value 20,000). This value gives the number of organisms in a milliliter of the given water sample (Mahmoud *et al.*, 2017).

Mathematically, the count per milliliter of water sample.

$X = N \times \text{reciprocal of the volume of the sample}$

$X = \text{dilution factor (i.e., } N \times V \times D)$

Where $V = (5 \times 10^{-8} \times 10)$

$D = \text{Dilution factor}$

Therefore, $X = (N \times 20 \times 10^7 \times D) \text{ cells/ml.}$

Results

Table 2: Microbiological analysis for hotels and suites A-E (Dry season)

S/n	Parameters CFU/ML	Cosmilla (A)	(B) De- Geogold	Sun- surge (C)	Mercy suite (D)	Queen suite (E)	WHO & EPA STD
1	STD plate count	801	1110	420	890	650	250 or fewer/1 ml
2	<i>E. coli</i>	13	11	01	08	01	0/100 ml
3	Coliform	22	14	06	12	05	100 or fewer100 ml
4	Pseudomonas	+ve	-ve	+ve	-ve	+ve	0/100 ml

Table 3: Microbiological analysis for hotels and suites F-J (Dry season)

S//n	Parameters CFU/ML	Jesse suite (F)	Golphen suite (G)	Trig- point (H)	Donrits (I)	Beautiful gate (J)	WHO & EPA STD
1	STD plate count	820	00	3000	00	320	250 or fewer/1 ml
2	<i>E. coli</i>	04	00	00	00	02	0/100 ml
3	Coliform	18	00	12	01	08	100 or fewer100 ml
4	Pseudomonas	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	0/100 ml

Table 4: Microbiological analysis for hotels and suites A-E (Rainy season)

S//n	Parameters CFU/ML	Cosmilla (A)	(B) De- Geogold	Sun- surge (C)	Mercy suite (D)	Queen suite (E)	WHO & EPA STD
1	STD plate count	860	520	560	905	950	250 or fewer/1 ml
2	<i>E. coli</i>	10	04	02	04	03	0/100 ml
3	Coliform	20	11	08	14	08	100 or fewer100 ml
4	Pseudomonas	+ve	+ve	+ve	-ve	-ve	0/100 ml

Table 5: Microbiological analysis for hotels and suites F-J (Rainy season)

S//n	Parameters	Jese suite (F)	Golphen suite (G)	Trig-point (H)	Donrits (I)	Beautiful gate (J)	WHO & EPA STD
1	STD plate count	820	00	3000	00	302	250 or fewer/1 ml
2	<i>E. coli</i>	04	00	00	00	02	0/100 ml
3	Coliform	18	00	12	01	08	100 or fewer100 ml
4	<i>Pseudomonas</i>	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	0/100 ml

Discussion

Two seasons were considered in this study –Dry and Rainy seasons- and the microorganisms tested were *E. coli*, Coliform, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The results obtained were compared with the World Health Organization (WHO) and the United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) standards for recreational water. During the dry season, there was 60% compliance for *E. coli*, for all the selected hotels and Suites. While in the rainy season, there was 50% compliance with respect to *E. coli* count. This implied that *E. coli* thrived more in the dry season in these hotels and suites. However, this is not universally true. While some studies have shown higher concentrations of *E. coli* during the dry season in specific locations and water sources, other research indicates the opposite, with higher concentrations during the rainy season. (Odonkor *et al.*, 2020). The prevalence of *E. coli* is influenced by various factors, including water source, human activity, and seasonal weather patterns. Seasonal variations had an impact on the concentration of *E. coli* both in water and sediments, with concentrations increasing during the wet season (Akebe *et al.*, 2015). In Burkina Faso, the majority of the population were more vulnerable to *E. coli* in the rainy season than in the dry season (Robert *et al.*, 2021).

There was 100% compliance for coliform in both the dry and rainy seasons. This is also an indication of the safety profile of these hotels and suites. Elsewhere in Osogbo, some coliforms were isolated from selected swimming pools, including *Shigella dysenteriae*, *Shigella paradysenteriae*, *Shigella sonnei*, and *Citrobacter freundii* (Ajadi *et al.*, 2017). In Port-Harcourt metropolis, the absence of coliform and fecal coliform bacteria (*E. coli*) revealed that the ten (10) swimming pools examined were within the WHO acceptable limits for certifying microbiological water quality (Amala *et al.*, 2016). In Ethiopia, only 27.8, 35.6, and 32.2% of swimming pools' water samples, respectively, met the WHO criterion for total coliform, fecal coliform, and heterotrophic plate count (Natnael *et al.*, 2024). In Edo State of Nigeria, the presence of pathogenic microorganisms including *E. coli*, total coliform count, and total bacteria count predisposes the users of these facilities to microbial infection (Ikhuorhiah *et al.*, 2024).

In the case of *P. aeruginosa*, there was 70% compliance in both the dry and rainy seasons. Swimmers who use swimming pools infected with *P. aeruginosa* are prone to various ailments, such as a "hot tub rash" (folliculitis or dermatitis) or "Swimmer's Ear" (Otitis externa). These are common indicators of *P. aeruginosa* presence in swimming pools. Other signs include skin infections, conjunctivitis, and even pneumonia or urinary tract infections in severe cases. *P. aeruginosa* was noted to be isolated in 50.8% of samples taken from nine selected swimming pools irrespective of free or total chlorine amount (Guida *et al.*, 2016). Approximately two-thirds (66.7%) of the examined swimming pool water samples in Egypt failed to meet the Egyptian standards of bacteriological indicators; *P. aeruginosa* was found in 26 (21.7%) of the samples (Aboufotouh *et al.*, 2017). Out of the 11,014 samples from 254 facilities in Spain, *P. aeruginosa* was isolated from 15.9% of the samples (Antonio *et al.*, 2023). In Lahore City, Punjab, Pakistan, 10 swimming pools in the study area were selected and evaluated for their microbial quality, and

P. aeruginosa was observed in 20% of the swimming pools (Chughtai *et al.*, 2025). The percentage *P. aeruginosa* count as observed in the selected swimming pools in Awka, the Capital City of Anambra State of Nigeria, was not only similar to what was obtained globally, but also better in some instances.

Conclusion

These swimming pools selected in Awka, Anambra State Capital, were relatively safe for recreational activities, though there were rooms for improvement. Donvits hotel and Golphin suite had the best microbial record because Donvits hotel had only 0.1 cfu/100 ml of coliform, and it's 100% free from all other tested microorganisms, while Golphin suite was 100% devoid of any of the tested microorganisms. Despite these feats by Donvits Hotel and Golphin suite, there is a need for constant treatment of swimming pool water to ensure their compliance with recreational water standards as stipulated by WHO and US EPA, and to reduce the risk of infections to the minimum possible.

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

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